

Estimating the quantization scale of space-time.

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Abstract

This paper argues that the length scale on which space time is quantized may be estimated from the energy of the photon emitted as an electron flips its spin state in a strong magnetic field.

e-, e+ pair creation in high energy photon scattering is taken as evidence that the electron (and the positron) each contain half a photon's worth of energy as a raised electrical potential. Our model for the pair creation event requires a photon's causal path to overlap itself twice. This attempt to impose 2 magnetic polarisations on one point in space at a single time breaks the causal path.

This causes the points to bifurcate in time, one half of each point is pushed off the current time plain into the future and the other into the past. These bifurcated points are presumably the smallest thing capable of holding an electromagnetic polarisation (a torsion field) and a causal link for a charging current (we call this the *g-bit* pronounced 'gobit').

The fact that space time exhibits chirality indicates the bifurcating points have shape. The paper argues that the energy released during an electron spin flip is a measure of the size of a *g-bit* and this is a likely value for the length scale at which space time is quantized.

This model for the quantization of space time exhibits behaviour like wave function collapse and allows information (charging currents) to flow backwards in time. The shortest possible time displacement from the current time plain is the width of a *g-bit* divided by the speed of light, this gives an estimate for the rest mass off a neutrino.

Keywords: *origin of spin 1/2 particles, origin of quantized charge, estimating the rest mass of a neutrino, Heisenberg struts, how force works*

1 Introduction

Electrons (and positrons) have a series of documented properties:

1. quantised charge [9].
2. spin of +/- 1/2 [2].
3. magnetic dipole moment [11, 10].
4. rest mass [5].
5. the g factor [6].
6. they can scatter photon inelastically [3].

Prior to this paper no satisfactory explanation has been given for why particle charge is quantized, what exactly gives rise to a spin 1/2 particle or why an electron should have a magnetic dipole moment. No explanation exists of the process by which a high energy gamma ray photon creates an electron/positron pair at a scattering event or any plausible explanation of what a neutrino is or what it is for.

This paper takes as its premise that there can be only one magnetic potential at a given point in space at an instant in time and looks at what happens when you try and insist potentials coexist.

e-, e+ pair creation in high energy photon scattering can be triggered by an interaction with a heavy particle or by interaction with a strong magnetic field [7, 8].

The model for an electron proposed in this paper predicts space time is quantized. For want of a better name we term the minimum sized chunk of space time capable of maintaining an electromagnetic torsion field a 'g-bit' or *gobit* of space time. It further requires that there is a causal path that information will have flowed along, where information passed from *gobit* to *gobit*. There seems to be a condensation process where charging currents (or information) can flow both forward and backwards in time.

The papers sets out the scattering conditions required for e-, e+ pair creation and term these type one *Hobson torsion field scattering* conditions where a high energy photon's causal path overlaps itself in two places. These are illustrated in section 2. The paper argues that fracturing a photon's causal path causes the two sections of the path that hold raised electric potential to collapse giving rise to a positron and an electron. The object that is created from a *gobit* in this path collapse is explored in section 2.1 and a stab is nearly made at predicting it's magnetic moment and an explanation is offered for spin and a value for the particle's intrinsic angular momentum is not calculated (section 2.4). The paths across the current time plane that carry the displacement current inside the electron are termed *Heisenberg struts* rather than bonds as they give rise to all of the mass in the universe. It is the cycling of information between the future and the past that gives a particle feedback on its surrounding.

Section 2.5.1 speculates neutrinos are just time dualled space time gobits but without the electric potential, they contain the shortest possible *Heisenberg struts* and thus have a predictable rest mass.

Section 2.1 assumes the difference in energy between a spin up and spin down electron represent a change in potential energy as a gobit is rotated in space and this is used to estimate a quantization length for space and time.

Section 2.5 indulges in rampant and irrelevant speculation and should not be read by serious scientists including the notion that a particle contains a record of its own near future and its near past. This makes the notion of time travel difficult as only the near past exists.

Conclusions are offered in section 3.

2 Hobson torsion field scattering events: crossing the streams.

Field lines form a pair of opposing magnetic north poles do not cross or merge. Attempting to force two (or more non parallel) magnetic polarisations to occupy the same point in space time has consequences and these have been known about since at least 1984 [1].

EGON: 'There's something very important I forgot to tell you.'
 PETER: 'What?'
 EGON: 'Don't cross the streams.'
 PETER: 'Why?'
 EGON: 'It would be bad.'
 PETER: 'I'm fuzzy on the whole good-bad thing. What do you mean, bad?'
 EGON: 'Try to imagine all life as you know it stopping instantaneously and every molecule in your body exploding at the speed of light.'
 RAY: 'Total protonic reversal.'

In reality this corresponds to the annihilation of a e^-e^+ pair through unwinding a matched pair of half photon bearing gobits of buggedgered space time and ironically crossing the streams may in fact be the mechanism for creating matter. Anyway it is lucky they did cross the streams or New York would have been destroyed by a giant marshmallow man.

Figure 2 shows a visualisation the electric and magnetic fields of a photon plotted along a time or space axis. It is by no means certain that is is a valid representation of what a photon is but the important part is that E and B are functions of Maxwell's 'displacement current'.

It is tempting to look at the distinct regions of raised +ve electric potential and -ve potential and just say 'there's your charge if you could just grab it and keep it still'. Fortunately there was one guy who was listening and his name was Werner Heisenberg.

Figure 1: Illustrative photon magnetic (blue) and electric (red) field strength along a time/space axis (black).

The magnetic potential of a photon is a vector quantity, it has a magnitude and a direction. It is not possible for a single point in space time to have two simultaneous magnetic potentials that differ in direction at a single time. This paper asks what happens when you really insist (on crossing the streams).

General Relativity [4] allows space time to be curved. In particular it allows for torsion fields to exist (eg magnetism). We introduce the notion of a causal path for a photon, this is equivalent to demanding that a photon identify which piece of potential caused which neighbouring piece of potential to change (where did the displacement current flow). Forcing a field onto a quantised grid is equivalent to wave function collapse from a superposition of states.

Figure 2 illustrates a torsion field causing the causal path of a photon to self intersect.

In order for a pair creation scattering event to occur type one *Hobson conditions* have to be met. These require that each of the separating loops contain half of a wavelength worth of the photon, specifically the e- loop must contain half of the wave with negative electric potential and the e+ loop must contain the half of the wave with positive electric potential. The energy of each half wave must be close to (and greater than) the rest mass of the electron.

Cutting the causal path leaves two orphaned arcs of space time. We now have to consider what a gobit of space time does. First and foremost it obeys Maxwell's equations and allows an electromagnetic wave to pass through it.

Maxwell's equations are written in their differential form as,

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \text{(Gauss's Law)} \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \text{(Gauss's Law for Magnetism)} \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \text{(Faraday's Law)} \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{J} + \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \text{(Ampère-Maxwell's Law)} \quad (4)$$

Maxwell's equation for electric and magnetic waves are:

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E} = \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}}{\partial t^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{B}}{\partial t^2} \quad (6)$$

The electric potential at a charge free point in space is given by:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \quad (7)$$

The magnetic field is perpendicular to the rate of change of electric field (referred to by Maxwell as the 'displacement current'). Figure 2 shows a cube of space time with electric potential, charging current and magnetic field. The charging current has to be able to enter the cube and exit it at a later time, its charging current input and output must be connected to something.

Reversing the direction of the flow of time in the green portion of the arc triggers the collapse of the separated arcs into single gobits of space time. The induced time reversal at the end points of the separating arcs connects their own outputs to their inputs but at an earlier time. This creates a dual particle that exists at two times. The charging current is passed forwards in time through one backwards in time through its dual (figure 2). This explanation is fuzzy at best but is a fuller and more causal explanation than that offered by Feynman's penguin diagrams.

In order for this to work the act of passing a charging current backwards in time through a gobit of space time seems to produce the same sign of potential but opposite polarisation of magnetic field. The charging current produces twice the magnitude of electric potential you would expect from the rest mass of the particle. The magnetic dipole of the particle is produced by a pair of N and S magnetic mono-poles with field strength equal to the maximum magnetic field in the half photon.

Figure 2 attempts to show the time looped particle.

The angular momentum of the particle is thought to come from the displacement currents which again will be counted twice as it loops through time.

The author is satisfied with the overall shape of the idea of time dualled g-bits but accepts that some of the details may not be exactly right.

The two spins of the electron arise from the direction of circulation of the displacement currents according to which magnetic pole is pushed forwards in time.

2.1 Estimating the size of a g-bit

The astute reader will notice that the charged surface of the g-bit in the time dualled particle may face inwards or outwards. This will lead to a small change in the stored potential energy of the particle. These two arrangements differ in whether the N pole is pushed forward in time or whether the S pole is pushed forward in time, this affects which direction the displacement currents rotate round the loop made by the Heisenberg struts. One direction of rotation will give rise to a spin +1/2 particle and the other to a spin -1/2 particle.

If the difference in energy required to flip between states is interpreted as a change in separation of the point charges then you have an estimate of the size of a g-bit.

For ease of following we write the working for this simple electro-statics problem in python. In this paper a electron is two identical point charges each with a point charge of half that of an electron separated by a distance r such that the self energy of the pair of charges is equal to the rest mass of the electron. The change in r associated with a change in rest mass equal to the energy from a spin flipping electron is referred to as dr . It is then assumed that separation in time is equivalent to $dt = dr/c$ where c is the speed of light. This lets you determine the Heisenberg spring constant for your local reality.

The author is assuming a separation in distance can be treated as an equivalent separation in time as $dt = dr/c$.

```
import numpy as np
import math
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Constants
q = 1.602176634e-19 # Charge of an electron (C)
epsilon_0 = 8.8541878128e-12 # Vacuum permittivity (F/m)
m = 9.1093837015e-31 # Mass of an electron (kg)
c = 299792458 # Speed of light (m/s)
k = 8.98755179e9 # Coulomb's constant

mvj = 1.602176634e-13

# plank
h = 6.62607015e-34;

# rest mass energy of electron
Uj = m * c**2

print('rest mass in Joules')
print( Uj)

#k = 8.98755179e9 # Coulomb's constant
#Eself = k * q1 * q2 / r

#self energy of two point charges separated by r
#Ue = k*(q/2) *(q/2) /r = Uj

print('self energy of two point charges e/2 = Uj separated by r')
B2r = k*(q/2) *(q/2)/Uj
print(B2r)
```

```

EspinFlip = 9.41170815267813e-25 #joules

# difference in efective radius
B2rf = k * q * q/((Uj - EspinFlip)*4)

print('spatial quantization size')
dr = B2rf - B2r
print(dr)

# separation of distance r in time dimension.
print('separation of distance r in time dimension. dt')
dt_r = B2r/c
print(dt_r)

# Heisenberg strut spring constant.
# force of replusion between 2 point charges a distance r apart.

# F = k * (q1 * q2) / r^2
# assuming a linear spring constant for time displacement.
# F = Hs * dt.
F = k * (q * q) / (4 * B2r**2)
print('force in N')
print(F)
Hs = F / (B2r)
print('Heisenberg spring constant in N/m')
print(Hs)

# rest mass of neutrino
Un = (Hs*dr**2)/2
Mn = Un/(c**2)

print('rest mass of neutrino')
print(Mn)

--- output ---
rest mass in Joules
8.187105776823886e-14
self energy of two point charges e/2 = Uj separated by r
7.044850813739913e-16
spatial quantization size
8.09854466061206e-27
separation of distance r in time dimension. dt
2.3499092874911193e-24
force in N
116.21404048551571
Heisenberg spring constant in N/m
1.6496309653407827e+17
rest mass of neutrino
6.019069551327487e-53

```

Figure 2.1 illustrates how the Heisenberg struts are stretched depending on which side of the g-bit the electric potential appears. The spring constant of the Heisenberg struts will balance self repulsion of the potentials. To a first approximation the difference in self energy can be taken as a change in separation.

2.2 Plotting electrical potential of a time dualled g-bit electron.

This paper assumes distance in time can be treated as just another orthogonal dimension (scaled by c , the speed of light) for the purposes of calculating electric potential. If an electric charge is off the time plane by time dt then the electric potential V at a point a distance r from the point in space becomes.

$$V = \frac{kq}{\sqrt{r^2 + (dt * c)^2}} \quad (8)$$

For a stationary electron the electric potential at a distance from a dualled g-bit at a distance dt from the current time plane would be

$$V = \frac{2kq}{\sqrt{r^2 + (dt * c)^2}} \quad (9)$$

Where q is half of the charge on electron. This is a much friendlier potential than a naked $1/r$ or $1/r^2$ one. Python to plot this kind of function is:

```
import numpy as np
import math
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Define the function
def f(r):
    return 1 / np.sqrt(r**2 + 1)

def g(r):
    gs = np.absolute( 1/r)
    return np.minimum(3,gs)

# Generate values for r
r_values = np.linspace(-10, 10, 500) # Generate 500 points between -10 and 10

# Calculate corresponding y-values
y_values = f(r_values)
y2 = g(r_values)

# Create the plot
plt.figure()
plt.plot(r_values, y_values)
plt.plot(r_values, y2, label='min(3, 1/r)')
plt.xlabel("r")
plt.ylabel("f(r) and max(2, 1/r)")
plt.title("Plot of f(r) = 1 / sqrt(r^2 + 1)")
```

```

plt.legend()
plt.grid(True)
plt.savefig('potential.eps', format='eps')

plt.show()

```

It is important to note that the 'charge' on the surface of a g-bit is counted twice.

Figure 2.2 shows a plot of a general $\frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2+1}}$ potential and a less well behaved $\frac{1}{r}$ potential. The time displacement of the charge centres neatly deals with the traditional mathematical issue of point charges.

2.3 Predicting the electron's magnetic dipole moment.

The author is going to admit he is unsure how to do this here at the time of writing. The magnetic field strength in the dual g-bits will simply be $B = E/c$. Where E is the peak electric field strength of the half photon that just spawn an e+ e- pair. Where the author is less clear is what dipole length to use and how to factor in the displacement current. There has to be a displacement current for there to be something to generate angular momentum from. What is less clear is does energy in the electron spend some time as electric and magnetic potential and some time as a displacement current? Does the energy oscillate forwards and backwards in time? The magnetic field associated with an electron is odd as it runs between two mono-poles that are separated in time and in space.

2.4 Angular momentum

It is clear that electrons have 'intrinsic' angular momentum. It is possible that the magnetic fields present with the time dualled g-bits of this model have to be diametrically opposed to each other and out of the plane in which the displacement current flows between g-bits. The displacement currents passing either side of the centre of the particle offer a tempting excuse for there being angular momentum. Displacement currents clearly convey energy so may have a mass equivalent. In which case they would give rise to angular momentum if they circulated round a centre. Again the author fails to put numbers to this.

2.5 Implications of the particle's structure.

Forcing static potential off the current time plane creates an object that has a location in the near past and in the near future. This permits a distinct object in space time to move in space without moving off the current time plane if there is a update cycle where the particle is able to send information from it's future self to its past self and visa versa.

The object itself encodes information about it's own velocity and location. Presumably this leads to measurement difficulties. It is not possible to simultaneously measure the particle's location in both the past and the future. This is a built in uncertainty principle.

The potential energy associated with the proximity of two electric charges is stored in the spring like Heisenberg struts. There is also the energy in the charging current. The particle is able to absorb energy which will be held in the Heisenberg struts until it can be re-radiated as electromagnetic radiation or translated directly into motion through changing the predicted future position of one half of the dual g-bit.

Time is encoded as a function of the speed of communication between g-bits. The past does not exist there is only the now and a recipe for how things will change with each directional update cycle.

The fact that the charge in and electron is split into two locations allows the particle to sample an electric field at two locations and get over the awkward fact a true point charge will not feel a force from a static electric field.

2.5.1 Neutrinos

It possible that a neutrino is a time dualled g-bit that contains no electric potential to stretch the Heisenberg struts. In order to exist as a particle that can move a particle must encode both its near past location and it's near future location relative to the current time plane. The spring constant for the Heisenberg struts can be calculated form the force between two point charges. This can then be used to estimate the energy required to stretch the minimum length struts to hold a time dualled g-bit of the current time plane. The python in the previous section gives an estimate for the rest mass of a neutrino as $6.019069551327487e-53$ Kg.

Given that neutrinos have spin identical to electrons it is probable that you can get a neutrino from an electron just by nicking its captured half photon (it can hop into a passing neutrino and turn that neutrino into an electron).

The author thinks it likely that protons and neutrons are a compounded structures made form 2 or 3 electron/positron scaffolds. It is therefore possible to measure neutrino flux by measuring the half life of a free neutron. The proposed mechanism for neutron decay has the interesting property that half lives of elements may vary in different portions of the universe if the local neutrino density varies.

3 Conclusions

This paper posits a model for a mechanism by which the fields from an electromagnetic wave can be trapped in particle form. The notion of a particle encoding it's own motion through straddling the *now* in time is both troubling and requires space time to be quantized. There is no obvious reason why the potential in the g-bit should have a fixed value in an electron beyond 'that is the maximum value that can be supported' and you need to hit this value to split a point in time.

The most obvious question remaining is how does space time support a torsion field in the first place. The whole thing looks alarmingly like a cheap simulation laid out across a vast self propagating information processing array. It seems to have all the hallmarks of a poorly thought through undergraduate experiment dreamed up in a bar and implemented on borrowed hardware. Basically the Great Green Arkleseizure and his drunken buddy the Flying Spaghetti Monster tried to build Deep Thought's replacement out of a bunch of spinny things that got hot or exploded when you stamped on them.

The ideas thrown into the world of theoretical physics by this paper will have to be completed by others.

4 Acknowledgements

The author acknowledges that the train of thought that lead to this paper started with a conversation at the Cambridge beer festival. I wanted a plausible space drive for a smutty scifi novel I was writing and things drifted to the subject of the Hobson GR Reaction mass less Torsion Drive (the Hobson Custard Drive) and how looking at quarks might provide a cheaper and less custardy alternative. The author acknowledges critical input of alcohol/pedantry from Mr Braben and Mr Ashfield. You simply can't get away form the fact that the force between quarks is spring like and the only fundamental thing in physics that behaves like a spring is Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and it involves time $\delta E \delta t = \lambda$.

References

- [1] Ghostbusters, 1984.
- [2] Jeremy Bernstein. The stern gerlach experiment, 2010. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1007.2435>.
- [3] Arthur H. Compton. The compton effect. *Physical Review*, 21(5):483–502, 1923.
- [4] A. Einstein. The foundation of the general theory of relativity. 1916.
- [5] Dean L Farnham, Robert S Van Dyck Jr, and Paul B Schwinberg. Determination of the electron’s atomic mass and the proton/electron mass ratio via penning trap mass spectroscopy. *Physical review letters*, 75(20):3598, 1995.
- [6] David J Griffiths. *Introduction to electrodynamics*. Pearson, 2013.
- [7] John D. Jackson. *Classical Electrodynamics*, volume 3. John Wiley & Sons, 1999.
- [8] Aimé Matheron, Jean-Raphaël Marquès, Vincent Lelasseux, Yinren Shou, Igor A. Andriyash, Vanessa Ling Jen Phung, Yohann Ayoul, Audrey Beluze, Ioan Dăncuș, Fabien Dorchies, Flanish D’Souza, Mathieu Dumergue, Mickaël Frotin, Julien Gautier, Fabrice Gobert, Marius Gugiu, Santhosh Krishnamurthy, Ivan Kargapolov, Eyal Kroupp, Livia Lancia, Alexandru Lazăr, Adrien Leblanc, Mohamed Lo, Damien Mataja, François Mathieu, Dimitrios Papadopoulos, Pablo San Miguel Claveria, Kim Ta Phuoc, Anda-Maria Talposi, Sheroy Tata, Călin A. Ur, Daniel Ursescu, Lidia Văsescu, Domenico Doria, Victor Malka, Petru Ghenuche, and Sebastien Corde. Compton photons at the gev scale from self-aligned collisions with a plasma mirror, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.19337>.
- [9] Robert Andrews Millikan. On the elementary electrical charge and the avogadro constant. *Physical Review*, 2(2):109, 1913.
- [10] C. Quigg. Notes on lepton gyromagnetic ratios. 2023. URL <https://lss.fnal.gov/archive/test-fn/1000/fermilab-fn-1129-t.pdf>.
- [11] John Tit. Electron magnetic dipole moment. 2023. URL https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electron_magnetic_moment.
- [12] W. C. Yi and T. J. Carroll. Electron electric dipole moment searches using clock transitions in ultracold molecules. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 125:153201, 2020. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.125.153201.

Figure 2: Evolution of a photons causal path over time in a GR torsion field. A Hobson scattering event occurs if the path overlaps itself at two points and if there is a photon of the right wavelength present in in the causal path at the right time.

g-bit of space time.

Figure 3: A *gobit* of space-time. It supports the transit of an electromagnetic wave (it supports a torsion field). Information flows through it between it's connections.

The electron as a time dualled g-bit.

Figure 4: A time dualled *gobit* of space-time. The upper and lower g-bits are the same particle but with displacement current flowing the opposite direction in time. The mutually repulsive force of the two point potentials is balanced by the Heisenberg struts. The Heisenberg struts carry the displacement current forward and backwards in time.

Figure 5: The difference between spin up spin down electrons. The Heisenberg struts are stretched while the apparent charge separation remains constant. To a first approximation the difference in self energy is a function of the change in Heisenberg strut length.

Figure 6: Illustrative plot of the shape of the experienced electric potential of the time dualled g-bit electron. Of course the potentials that create the field exists in the past and the future not in the now. There are no infinities in the measured field in the now.